

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) 220906xt_0m

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: 220906xt_0m

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0098 Å Wavelength=1.34139

Cell: a=11.785 (8) b=18.436 (13) c=20.766 (15)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 296 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	4512 (5)	4512 (5)
Space group	P 21 21 21	P 21 21 21
Hall group	P 2ac 2ab	P 2ac 2ab
Moiety formula	C21 H25 N O7	C21 H25 N O7
Sum formula	C21 H25 N O7	C21 H25 N O7
Mr	403.42	403.42
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.188	1.188
Z	8	8
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.475	0.475
F000	1712.0	1712.0
F000'	1716.45	
h, k, lmax	14, 22, 25	14, 22, 25
Nref	8607 [4784]	8571
Tmin, Tmax	0.967, 0.977	0.535, 0.751
Tmin'	0.967	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.535 Tmax=0.751
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.79/1.00 Theta (max)= 54.972

R(reflections)= 0.0686 (5052)

wR2(reflections)=
0.2135 (8571)

S = 0.994

Npar= 564

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT221_ALERT_2_C	Solv./Anion Resd 2 C	Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	4.4	Ratio
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	O4A --C19A	6.3	s.u.
PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	C20A --C21A	6.6	s.u.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference	C1C --C14	0.21	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference	C14 --C15	0.21	Ang.
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of			C13 Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of			C14 Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of			C13A Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of			C14A Check
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of			C20A Check
PLAT260_ALERT_2_C	Large Average Ueq of Residue Including	O1A	0.102	Check
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds		0.00977	Ang.
PLAT368_ALERT_2_C	Short C(sp2)-C(sp2) Bond	C20 - C21	1.23	Ang.
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600	18	Report

● **Alert level G**

ABSMU01_ALERT_1_G	Calculation of _exptl_absorpt_correction_mu			
	not performed for this radiation type.			
PLAT002_ALERT_2_G	Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite		9	Note
PLAT003_ALERT_2_G	Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ...		13	Report
PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms		2	Report
PLAT072_ALERT_2_G	SHELXL First Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large		0.14	Report
PLAT172_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains DFIX Records		1	Report
PLAT176_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SADI Records		4	Report
PLAT178_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SIMU Records		4	Report
PLAT301_ALERT_3_G	Main Residue Disorder(Resd 1)		10%	Note
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O2		106.9	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O2A		107.5	Degree
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels		9	Note
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1 (Sohnke SpGr)		S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1A (Sohnke SpGr)		S	Verify
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints		109	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600		5	Note
PLAT913_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF		2	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File		3	Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		0	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
14 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
19 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

1 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
17 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
5 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
9 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/05/2022; check.def file version of 17/05/2022

